

Curriculum, Conceptions, and Classroom Practice: A Literature-Informed Analysis of Scientific Literacy and the Nature of Science

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This paper synthesises key literature on scientific literacy and the Nature of Science (NoS) to identify current understanding, persistent definitional challenges and opportunities for future research. Scientific literacy has long been recognised as a central goal of science education, and conceptions of scientific literacy have continued to evolve, moving from a focus on the acquisition of scientific knowledge towards the application of this knowledge to make informed decisions. This shift reflects the growing emphasis on nurturing active, informed citizens who can address global issues in a sustainable and ethical manner. Developing students' understanding of NoS is widely recognised as a key mechanism for nurturing scientific literacy, and internationally there has been a move to embed NoS within curricula. This is reflected in Ireland where NoS is now a fundamental element of Primary, Junior and Senior Cycle science curricula. While the inclusion of NoS across Irish curricula is a positive development, its impact will be limited without effective professional learning for teachers. Studies continue to reveal significant gaps in teachers' understanding of NoS and they highlight the need to strengthen teachers' pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) for effective NoS instruction. Future research must investigate current levels of teachers' NoS understanding in Ireland which should then be used to inform the design of targeted, research-informed supports. Only then can the aims of curricular reform, and the broader vision of nurturing scientifically literate citizens, be realised.

Key Words: Scientific Literacy, Nature of Science (NoS), Science Education, Curricular Reform, Misinformation

Highlights

- This paper examines the connection between scientific literacy, NoS and broader global goals.
- This paper examines key literature on scientific literacy and NoS.
- This paper identifies priorities for future research on NoS and scientific literacy.

Scientific Literacy

For decades, researchers and policymakers have responded to global challenges by trying to prepare students to thrive in rapidly changing societies (Tytler *et al.*, 2025). Today's world presents a range of pressing and complex challenges which require citizens who can engage in public discourse and take informed action (Siarova, Sternadel and Szonyi, 2019). While societies have always grappled with the pressing problems of their time, the modern landscape of misinformation and disinformation presents complex challenges. An understanding of scientific literacy and NoS is essential so that citizens can “evaluate the claims made in the name of science and act accordingly” (McComas, 2021, p. 11). ‘Scientific literacy for all’ may appear to be an intuitive solution to contemporary challenges (Sharon and Baram-Tsabari, 2020), but achieving it is far from straight-forward.

Nurturing a scientifically literate population has been a fundamental goal of science education since the 1950s (Siarova, Sternadel and Szonyi, 2019). Scientific literacy encompasses a broad range of goals that educators, scientists and policymakers hold for individuals and society, tied together by a shared yet loosely defined understanding (Osborne, 2023). As the aims of science education evolve, definitions of scientific literacy require continuous refinement (Lee and Zhai, 2025). However, Rudolph (2024) argues that this is counterproductive, as the fixation on precise definitions and conceptions of scientific literacy hinders meaningful progress in schools and communities. While conceptual clarity is important, there is a risk that theoretical debates may eclipse the focus on actionable strategies. Without a careful balance between developing a coherent understanding of scientific literacy and embedding it through practical strategies, efforts to promote it risk becoming abstract and disconnected from classroom realities. While the debate concerning a precise definition persists, certain ideas have been particularly influential in shaping both conceptions of scientific literacy and its integration into educational policy.

Roberts (2007) proposed a prominent model with two influential visions of scientific literacy denoted by Roman numerals. ‘Vision I’ relates to the products and processes of science, whereas ‘Vision II’ relates to the application of scientific knowledge to everyday life (Roberts, 2007). ‘Vision III’ was later conceptualised and discussed by Yore (2012) and Osborne (2023) to reflect the contemporary goals of science education. The achievement of scientific literacy through the lens of ‘Vision III’, results in active citizens who can engage with socio-scientific issues (SSIs), like climate change and biodiversity loss, through debate and action (Yore, 2012). The PISA 2015 Framework defined scientific literacy as the “ability to engage with science-related issues, and with the ideas of science, as a reflective citizen”

(OECD, 2017, p. 22). This definition, which strongly reflects ‘Vision II’, is the most widely used (Osborne, 2023), and it is the only definition explicitly adopted within Irish curricular documents.

Changes to the Junior Cycle science curriculum made in 2015, and the new Senior Cycle and Primary science curricula introduced in 2025, represent progress in terms of the inclusion and prominence of scientific literacy in science education (NCCA, 2015, 2024, 2025). These curricular changes are reflective of ‘Vision I’ and ‘Vision II’, which prioritise disciplinary knowledge and its application to daily life. While ‘Vision I’ and ‘Vision II’ laid the foundation of our modern view of scientific literacy, ‘Vision III’ presents a sustainability focused framework aligned with global goals that highlights the need for active, empowered citizens (Kumar and Choudhary, 2025). The current curricular changes offer more scope to nurture student agency. However meaningful progress towards ‘Vision III’ will depend on the support provided for teachers as they work to empower students to engage with SSIs and global challenges. It is essential that a shared and coherent understanding of scientific literacy is established, alongside the clear articulation and communication of the aims of the curricular changes. Crucially, these efforts must be underpinned by high-quality professional learning for teachers so that meaningful progress can be made.

From Scientific Literacy to the NoS

Developing an understanding of NoS has long been regarded as one of the keys to achieving scientific literacy (Bell, Lederman and Abd-El-Khalick, 2000; Yacoubian, 2021), as it supports students as they engage with SSIs (Allchin, Møller Andersen and Nielsen, 2014; Murphy, Smith and Broderick, 2021), and evaluate scientific claims (McComas, 2021). NoS has also become an important element of science education in Ireland, and it is now a key curricular strand underpinning the entire curriculum in Junior and Senior Cycle science subjects (NCCA, 2015, 2024). While there is widespread agreement that improving NoS understanding is an important educational outcome (Lederman and Lederman, 2014), the most effective strategies for achieving this, and indeed the precise definition of NoS, have sparked ongoing debate. For decades philosophers, historians, researchers, and scientists have struggled to generate an agreed upon, widely accepted definition of the NoS (Lederman, 2013). Despite this, it is accepted that NoS pertains to the epistemology of science (Bell, Lederman and Abd-El-Khalick, 2000; Lederman, 2013). McComas (2021, p. 10) suggests that NoS “tells us the rules of the game of science” which all scientific endeavours roughly follow.

Over the decades NoS researchers identified a set of overlapping, but not identical, elements of NoS which have underpinned much of the research to date (Abd-El-Khalick and Lederman, 2023). These elements have shaped what is often referred to as the ‘consensus view’ of NoS, which describes some key ideas about science and how scientific knowledge develops (Abd-El-Khalick, 2012). The consensus view has evolved over the decades, and it highlights that science should be empirical, inferential, theory-driven, tentative, socially negotiated, and culturally embedded (Abd-El-Khalick and Lederman, 2023). While other prominent models exist, like the Family Resemblance Approach (Irzik and Nola, 2011), the consensus model remains the most widely used in NoS research (Abd-El-Khalick and Lederman, 2023). In today’s landscape of conflicting funding sources and widespread misinformation, an understanding of the NoS is more crucial than ever. When students understand NoS it equips them with the critical thinking skills needed to evaluate scientific claims and discern credible knowledge from misleading or biased information. To distinguish scientific fact from misinformation students must understand how science works and grasp what type of knowledge is deemed to be scientific and credible (Lee and Zhai, 2025). The consensus view provides teachers with a practical framework to help their students navigate an increasingly complex societal landscape.

With scientific literacy and NoS firmly embedded in the curriculum, the key question is how to best support teachers’ and students’ developing understanding. Between the 1960s and 1980s, research consistently found that students were not developing a meaningful understanding of NoS (Khishfe and Lederman, 2006) and more recent studies have continued to echo these findings (Cofré *et al.*, 2019; van Griethuijsen *et al.*, 2015). Historically, designing interventions for teachers to implement in the classroom was considered as a mechanism for improving student understanding (Lederman and Lederman, 2014), however for the most part, students’ conceptions of NOS remained naïve following the interventions (Khishfe and Lederman, 2006). These studies initially overlooked the potential impact of teachers’ understanding and classroom practice on the success of these programmes (Lederman, 2013; Lederman and Lederman, 2014). As “teachers cannot possibly be expected to teach content that they do not understand themselves” (Dogan and Abd-El-Khalick, 2008, p. 1102), improving teachers’ understanding was recognised as a prerequisite for NoS learning (McComas, 1998) and this has been reflected in the majority of NoS studies conducted since (Abd-El-Khalick and Lederman, 2023). However, research consistently reveals gaps in teachers’ understanding of NoS (Vázquez-Alonso *et al.*,

2013; Abd-El-Khalick and Lederman, 2023) which is concerning given that science teachers have a crucial role to play in nurturing students' understanding of NoS and their scientific literacy (Firestone *et al.*, 2012).

While curricular changes in Ireland have highlighted the importance of NoS, teachers need support, curricular resources, and evidence-based strategies to teach it effectively. Since 2013, two thirds of NoS research studies focused on improving teachers' understanding while only one third focused on improving their ability to teach it (Abd-El-Khalick and Lederman, 2023). Research shows that an explicit (Khishfe, 2023; Valencia Narbona, Núñez Nieto and Cofré Mardones, 2023), integrated (Khishfe and Lederman, 2006) and reflective (Adibelli-Sahin and Deniz, 2017) approach is best for supporting students' understanding of NoS. Consequently, enhancing teachers' pedagogical practices has emerged as a prerequisite to effective NoS instruction. PCK refers to the crossover between understanding the content and understanding the best way to teach the content in a manner that addresses students' preconceptions and misconceptions (Shulman, 1986). Recent studies have shown that improving teachers' PCK enhances classroom practice which enables students to deepen their understanding of NoS and connect school science to the real-world (Murphy, Smith and Broderick, 2021).

Future directions of Research

Citizens need more than knowledge to tackle 21st century issues, they need to work individually and collaboratively to make sustainable and responsible decisions for the future of the planet (Broderick, 2023; Monroe *et al.*, 2023). Scientific literacy and developing an understanding of NoS will support students to develop these competencies, but meaningful progress will ultimately depend on what happens in classrooms. Decades of research demonstrate that simply articulating curricular goals is insufficient; teachers need the PCK required to teach NoS and empower their students to engage with science in the real-world. Achieving this requires a consistent and coherent understanding of NoS across school science, professional learning, and teacher education programmes (Dogan and Abd-El-Khalick, 2008).

Future research should prioritise teacher education and professional learning that enhances understanding and develops the PCK required for effective NoS instruction. As post-primary teachers in Ireland have been facilitating explicit NoS learning for over a decade at Junior Cycle, it is timely to examine their current understanding. Such research will enable the development of targeted interventions that integrate both content knowledge and

pedagogy which will be essential to the success of upcoming curricular reforms. Changes to the curriculum are a move in the right direction. However, sustained and intentional professional learning for teachers is essential to nurture scientifically literate citizens capable of navigating misinformation, taking action, and contributing thoughtfully and meaningfully to society.

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